

SURF ZONE INSTRUMENTED DRIFTER DOCUMENTATION

1 - Components

The instrumented drifter is composed of two major components - the internal **electronics cluster** and the external **enclosure**

Image 1: Drifter Electronics Cluster with exposed boards

1.1 - Electronics Cluster

The electronics cluster is comprised of off-the-shelf components:

- Four main boards:
 - Teensy 3.2 Microcontroller Board
 - *Micro USB output for uploading code and diagnosing the drifter*
 - Adafruit GPS
 - Pimoroni IMU
 - Pololu MicroSD Card Reader
 - *Instrument data is written to the MicroSD*
- 3.2V Battery
- Status Indicator LED

The electronics cluster is built around three custom-printed PLA cage pieces designed to slot into the negative space of the enclosure.

Image 2: 3D Printed Electronics Cluster Pieces from Incept3D

The entire electronics cluster can be removed from the enclosure as necessary for diagnosing problems or repairs by using quick-disconnect JST-2.0 connectors with the enclosure switch and battery. This also allows individual clusters to be moved between enclosures if necessary, or vice-versa

Image 3: Open Drifter with disconnected JST connectors

A wiring diagram of the electronics cluster and a BOM of the entire drifter can be seen on the following pages.

FIGURE 1: DRIFTER ELECTRONICS SCHEMATIC

FIGURE 2: DRIFTER BILL OF MATERIALS

#	Qty per	Component	Alt	Part information (description)	manufacturer	Manufacturer part #	Part information (manufacturer)	Misc.
1	1	MICRO-CONTROLLER	TEENSY		PJRC	Teensy 3.2	PJRC Teensy 4.0	Part of Dutek Assembly
2	1	GPS		Sensor	Adafruit	PA1010D	Mini GPS PA1010D	
3	1	IMU		Sensor	Pimoroni	ICM20948	Pimoroni ICM20948	
4	1	MICROSD BREAKOUT	SD CARD READER	Writes collected data to microSD	Pololu	2597	Pololu microSD Breakout Board #2597	
5	1	BATTERY			EEMB	502030	EEMB 3.7V Li-ion 502030	
6	1	LED		Status indicator - 2-pin LED	/	/	/	Part of Dutek Assembly
7	1	RESISTOR		For LED	/	/	/	
8	1	CONNECTOR (MALE)	JST MALE	Used in battery-switch circuit	/	/	JST-PH 2.0	
9	2	CONNECTOR (FEMALE)	JST FEMALE					
10	1	SWITCH		Located in battery circuit, operates sensor through watertight enclosure	ITW	48-2-RB-N-R D-B	ITW 48-2-RB-N-RD-B	
11	2	GPS SCREW	M2 SCREW	Secures the Adafruit GPS to the PLA plate opposite the IMU				Part of Dutek Assembly
12	2	GPS NUT	M2 NUT					
13	4	ENCLOSURE SCREW	M2.5 SCREW	Secures the two halves of the enclosure together.				
14	4	ENCLOSURE NUT	M2.5 NUT					
15	1	ENCLOSURE O-RING	031 O-RING	Seals the two enclosure halves			MR-N70031/25	
16	1	SLA PIECE 1	EXTERNAL ENCLOSURE (NUT)	Enclosure half that seats the switch and electronics and is secured by four M2.5 nuts	Incept3D	/	/	Custom
17	1	SLA PIECE 2	EXTERNAL ENCLOSURE (BOLT)	Enclosure half that is transparent and is secured by four M2.5 screws.	Incept3D	/	/	Custom
18	1	PLA PIECE 1	INTERNAL SCAFFOLD	Holds SD card reader in place internally, as well as PLA pieces 2 and 3 in place internally.	Incept3D	/	/	Custom
19	1	PLA PIECE 2	TEENSY PLATE	Holds microcontroller in place internally	Incept3D	/	/	Custom
20	1	PLA PIECE 3	GPS-IMU PLATE	Holds GPS and IMU in place internally	Incept3D	/	/	Custom

2.1 - Assembly (Electronics)

The electronics cluster can be assembled with off-the-shelf parts and tools. Of the original 20 drifter set, 3 were manufactured in-house and 17 were manufactured by Dutek Electronics Assembly in Vista, CA; with an assembly based off of the the three original prototypes.

Image 4: Electronics Cluster in PLA Cage

2.1.1 - Fabrication by Hand

<WIP>

2.2 - Assembly (Enclosure)

The enclosure is assembled of two major hemisphere components - the lower red-opaque piece and the upper transparent piece. The electronics cluster is meant to seat in the red-opaque hemisphere with the transparent hemisphere as the “lid,” as the SD card and Micro USB are facing outwards from the red hemisphere.

2.2.1 - Enclosure Switch

Before assembling the hemispheres as well, the red hemisphere must be seated with the IP-67 AEW switch.

Image 5: Properly Seated Switch

The AEW switch has an exact orientation that it may be seated into the enclosure, indicated by a divot in the switch body that aligns with a divot in the switch port in the enclosure

The o-ring/gasket included with the AEW switch should be lightly coated with silicone grease and placed on the switch body before seating

After placing the switch through the switch port, it should be tightened from the inside using the included nut and a pair of pliers.

Once the switch is seated and tightened in place, the electronics cluster may be placed inside the red-opaque enclosure half. The switch protrusion should align with the backside of the battery, which is the side of the electronics cluster that features more negative space.

2.2.2 - Battery

The BATTERY must be placed in the electronics cluster before being placed in the enclosure, since the battery is placed and removed from the **bottom** of the electronics cluster. The battery cannot be placed in the electronics cluster when the cluster is already seated in the enclosure at risk of damaging wire hookups on the microcontroller. The battery should be placed in the electronics cluster with the JST connected at the **bottom**, and the cable should be routed up to the top of the cluster in line with negative space adjacent to the GPS or IMU.

Image 6: Proper Battery Placement

2.2.3 - JST Connectors & Notes on Placing the Electronics in the Enclosure

When placing the electronics cluster in the enclosure, it is important to make sure no wires are conflicting between the PLA cage of the electronics cluster and the inner shell of the enclosure. The most important cables to note for this clearance are the BATTERY (black and red JST) and the SD CARD Reader (green). The electronics cluster should seat relatively easily, and should not be forced into the enclosure.

*Image 7:
BAD - Cables and JST
connectors interfere with
the o-ring Flange*

*Image 8:
GOOD - Cables do not
interfere with o-ring
flange*

After the cluster is seated in the enclosure, the JST connectors from the Microcontroller should be connected to the enclosure switch and the battery. The connectors should be held in the negative space around the battery and switch, and if necessary, the negative space adjacent to the microcontroller opposite of the SD card.

At this stage, if the drifter is previously unused, an SD card should be inserted and code should be loaded onto the electronics cluster before the drifter is sealed. Instructions for this can be found in OPERATION.

2.2.4 - Closing the Drifter

Before placing the second half of the enclosure on top and sealing the container, the 031 o-ring should be cleaned and re-greased with a small (~2 grains of rice) drop of silicone grease. For ease of assembly, this o-ring should be placed on the flange of the red half of the enclosure.

Image 9: Prepared drifter with electronics and 031 o-ring

When placing the transparent half of the enclosure on top, it is necessary to again make sure that no wires are pinching around the o-ring flange. The most important ones to make note of are the battery and switch hookup cables, as well as the MicroSD Card reader wires (green)

Once the hemispheres are mated, it may be useful to hold them together with a rubber band or small clamp.

Four m2.5 nuts and bolts are used to seal the enclosure. The nuts are seated in the red hemisphere and the bolts should be placed through the transparent hemisphere.

Images 10 & 11: Enclosure halves with bolts (transparent) and nuts (red)

A pair of bolts opposite each other should be tightened first in order to better distribute compressive force during the sealing of the enclosure.

Be careful to not over-tighten the enclosure. At this time there is no torque spec for sealing the enclosure, but a **good rule of the thumb** is to tighten the enclosure until the red and transparent halves are making contact on the fins.

2.2.5 - Drifter Leash

In order to prevent the loss of a drifter and ease in the retrieval of a drifter, each drifter is deployed with an attached leash and float system. Leashes are constructed separately from drifters and are attached at deployment to the holes on either side of the red half of the enclosure.

Leashes have 4 parts:

- Float ("Peanut Float")
- Roughly 30ft of braided fishing line
 - *Measuring out long lengths of line can be tedious. My go-to system for measuring 30 ft of line is using the two small table clamps in the large lab toolbox, placing them at either end of the white 8'2" table, and running line back and forth four times to measure out ~32' of line (-AV)*
- Two double-barrel fishing line crimps
 - *A crimping tool specifically for assembling the drifter leash is in the project tool box*
- One welded fishing line snap hook

FIGURE 3: LEASH ASSEMBLY

Image 12: Drifters ready for deployment leashed to floats

3 - Operation (WIP)

3.1 - Setting Up a New Drifter or Updating an Existing Drifter

3.1.1 - Error Codes

3.2 - Deployment

3.3 - Offloading Data from a Drifter